

USE OF AI TOOLS FOR INNOVATIVE LESSON PLANS AND EFFECTIVE TEACHING LEARNING: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Nowadays, the application of AI has become commonplace and due to the vast range of possibilities enabled by Artificial Intelligence, workers and organizations in every sector are able to enhance their operational functions by using technologies that provide detailed reports, integrated plans, useful resources and even suggest activities to enhance decision-making processes. This study briefly delves into the educational spectrum, in conjunction with AI tools that have been used or implemented lately. In short, this article explores how AI tools have innovated teaching methods, helped educators in reaching their goals and empowered academicians by turning complex operations into simplified tasks. We shall go through the ways in which AI improved lesson-planning, by introducing features for personalization, data analysis, customization, resource recommendations and so on. We shall also examine particular areas in AI that have predominantly been applied, such as Generative AI, including its abominable impacts in education and learning.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence in Education, Generative AI in education, Machine Learning*

Introduction

AI can be defined as a form of technology or “computing system” that can indulge in human work processes and can learn, adapt, correct, analyze and use data to render complex tasks. In the educational landscape, it essentially provides educators with a basic framework, like details, recommendations, probabilities and learning-resources that suit the classroom’s needs. AI understands the individual’s requirement instantly, through prompts or keywords,

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and produces frameworks, upon which educators or teachers can strategize elaborate methods and long-term academic goals. Usually, it took hours for educators to formulate such initial frameworks, mind-maps or ideas. Now, educators are able to save a substantial amount of time by using AI and formulate effective strategies.

Generative AI has come under immense speculation too, due to its revolutionary features. It is a field of AI that basically enables computing systems to generate human-like images, texts and sounds, through the use of Machine Learning algorithms. “These algorithms analyze and replicate the structure and characteristics of specific types of content to create new content that mimics the original, in response to complex and multimodal prompts” (Banh & Strobel, 2023; Karpathy, 2016; Lim, 2023).

Inquiry-based learning (IBL)

IBL can be defined as a “constructivist paradigm” that includes both students and teachers in the process of knowledge and meaning construction. It encourages an in-depth learning of subjects and raises students’ motivation by making the learning process interesting and insightful. IBL ensures that students are actively involved in the learning and knowledge-creation process. Conventional teaching methods used to apply a structured form of inquiry into topics, whereas IBL enables a broader and open-minded form of inquiry, thus providing the scope to form new meanings from subjects. This spectrum or form of open-minded inquiry creates a balance between the autonomy of students and guidance provided by teachers. The emphasis falls upon the student's independence to learn rather than the educator’s control to teach.

Compared to traditional teaching methods, adaptive learning promoted by IBL, enables students to retain their interest in subjects. Furthermore, students were observed to have gotten better at conceptual learning and became well-acquainted with subjects that include complex theories, functions and so on. However, the complexities of implementing such advanced systems into the educational spectrum is also noteworthy. Firstly, a teacher's competency must be noted, so as to avoid hindrances in the classroom. This requires institutions to run special programmes that train educators, into using new forms of technology, altogether innovating the operations of a classroom. Covering the entire course/curriculum becomes a challenge too. IBL is a resource-intensive method, which means one must have complete access to various types of resources at all times, so as to avoid inadequate time-consumption and vain efforts.

Content recreation

Generative AI has enabled educators to indulge in the task of content recreation. Such concepts have helped universities and institutions improve their course-structure by creating interdisciplinary programmes, integrated with the usage of technologies GenAI and Machine learning algorithms to improve the teaching/learning process. “GenAI is the technology behind Large Language Models (LLMs), such as OpenAI's Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) and Google's Gemini. The widely known ChatGPT is the chat interface of the GPT-3 model and its successors. Beyond LLMs, there is a variety of other models of GenAI, such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) and diffusion models” (Moundridou, Matzakos, Doukakis, 2024). Such forms of technology have been used to develop applications, methods and courses that have simply recreated the entire educational landscape.

Research also suggests how GenAI provides both pedagogical and functional opportunities for teachers, ones that may influence changes into their curriculum and methods used for assessments. It is worth noting that the priority of AI in education is to develop or create resources for teaching, rather than multimodal forms/applications. Content recreation has come a long way, especially after the advent of tools like ChatGPT. It is evident that OpenAI's recent innovation has enabled users to recreate content to make it more insightful and exploratory. It promotes personalized learning, comprehensive reading, assessments and more. Let's have a look at these salient features

Personalization:

AI analyzes data to produce better results. Through such a course of action, teachers can spot out the strengths and weaknesses of students, altogether providing the basis to adapt and improvise strategies, and specifically address those weaknesses or harness those strengths.

Resource recommendation:

Finding essential resources becomes a tedious task when the nature of the topic is vast or diverse. In this regard, AI makes the process of lesson-planning far more efficient and time-saving, as it focuses on specific areas where students face trouble or confusion, provides resources/recommendations and alternative teaching methods to manifest better results. Such resources include books, journals, references and articles that are relevant to the particular subject or lesson being taught. AI is capable of suggesting interactive methods to boost student engagement.

Efficacy and adaptive learning:

Automated technology essentially saves a lot of time, as it instantly generates comprehensive lesson-plans, gathers necessary resources and provides suggestive measures to curb prevalent issues. As AI assists vibrantly with the planning and structuring process, teachers inevitably get more time to interact with students and engage in a personalized manner to reach understand and teach them effectively.

Conclusion

AI has provided incessant leaps by instantly coming up with ideas, solutions and lesson-plans. The advanced usage of Machine Learning algorithms has aided the cause of content recreation, hence enabling the academic realm to indulge in knowledge-creation and derive greater meanings from conventional topics/subjects. AI essentially saves a lot of time for teachers and provides alternative teaching methods. This in-turn allows teachers to engage with students on a personal-level and understand their problematic areas with better insights or profundity. AI tools have proven their efficiency by manifesting actual changes in the educational sectors. It has improved the teaching/learning process by making the initial planning stages swift and efficient. It also provides teachers a scope to improvise and explore different teaching methods, ones that are better suited for their (respective) classroom. AI also improved curriculum-designs, by allowing educators to pin-point or focus on specific areas, hence enabling them to introduce subjects/courses that align with the larger interest of the institution and students. The innovations are rampant, which is why there's a greater need to create learning programmes for teachers, so that they get well-acquainted with the technologically-driven landscape in education, or any other sector in a broader context.

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